

SURROGATE MODEL-DRIVEN AUTOMATION FOR RVE DESIGN AND VALIDATION OF LONG DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A physics-informed surrogate-modeling framework is presented for automated RVE generation, validation, and rapid prediction of effective stiffness in aligned discontinuous carbon fiber composites. A fully Python-driven workflow within Abaqus creates 2D representative volume elements (RVEs) parameterized by fiber length, gap, width, angle, and volume fraction. Convergence studies show that including three repeating units of the fiber-gap pattern within the RVE is sufficient to capture microstructural variability without requiring periodic boundary conditions. A 200 sample 0 degree dataset trains three Random Forest regressors: one each for E_{11} , G_{12} , and the Halpin–Tsai shape factor $\xi_{E_{11}}$. Validation on $\theta = 0^\circ$ yields $R^2 > 0.970$ and MAE < 0.07 GPa for E_{22} and G_{12} , while $\xi_{E_{11}}$ achieves $R^2 > 0.975$. Embedding these predictions in a Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) framework enables accurate modulus prediction across arbitrary fiber angles, with E_{11} and E_{22} remaining within 10% of full-FEA across arbitrary fiber angles. This consistency inspires confidence in the FEA data as its trends align with well-established composite analytical models. Beyond prediction, the surrogate model is used to identify and filter anomalous simulations, a particularly important capability for angled fibers, where meshing and loading artifacts frequently corrupt results. By integrating micromechanical models, laminate theory, and machine learning, this hybrid framework bridges physical intuition with data-driven inference. It enables the rapid generation of large, validated property datasets at a fraction of the cost of full FEA. These datasets are well-suited for future inverse design workflows, where optimal discontinuous fiber architectures must be identified for target stiffness requirements.

1 INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous fiber-reinforced composites (DFRCs) combine fiber segments within a polymer matrix, offering scalability and automation advantages over continuous fiber composites (CFRCs). While CFRC processes often involve high labor and tooling costs, DFRCs offer a cost-effective alternative with improved recyclability, and compatibility with complex geometries [1,2]. Recent advances in robotic fiber placement and AI-driven control have significantly enhanced DFRC mechanical performance, bringing tensile strength and stiffness closer to CFRC benchmarks [3,4]. Moreover, aligned DFRCs enable spatial control of stiffness, strength, and energy absorption, allowing mechanical behavior to be tailored to application specific loading through inverse design. The success of such inverse design efforts, aimed at identifying optimal microstructures to achieve target macroscopic properties, relies on the ability to generate large, accurate datasets that reflect the influence of fiber architecture on mechanical response.

Existing FEA based datasets are often constrained by manually generated fiber geometries, inconsistent boundary condition implementations, and limited control over key design parameters such as fiber length, gap, and orientation. Numerous prior studies utilize idealized or overly simplified microstructures, which fail to reflect the parametric complexity of aligned discontinuous fiber configurations. For such systems, accurate prediction of load transfer and stiffness anisotropy demands

precise geometric fidelity and consistent numerical formulations. Furthermore, meshing artifacts and numerical instability, particularly in off axis fiber alignments, result in high simulation failure rates and reduce the reliability of computed property data [5,6]. Automated workflows for representative volume element (RVE) generation and validation in aligned DFRCs remain limited, restricting the scalability and fidelity of data driven inverse modeling.

To address these constraints and enable scalable inverse design, a set of computational tools is being developed in conjunction with a gantry mounted robotic aligned DFRC manufacturing platform engineered to physically implement the methods established in this study. In parallel, a fully automated process for RVE generation, validation, and surrogate model training has been established to overcome modeling limitations associated with manual fiber placement and simulation inconsistency. A Python driven Abaqus workflow generates 2D RVEs parameterized by fiber length, interfiber gap, width, orientation angle, and volume fraction. Convergence studies determine the minimum number of fiber segment repetitions required to capture statistically representative behaviour without the need for periodic boundary conditions. Physics informed validation is performed using micromechanical models, including the Halpin–Tsai formulation for predicting longitudinal stiffness and a series rule model for estimating transverse and shear stiffness components [7–9]. Until the manufacturing platform is fully operational, high fidelity FEA datasets generated within the research group serve as the primary basis for training and validating inverse design methodologies.

Building on this validated dataset, a machine learning surrogate is trained to predict both the Halpin–Tsai shape factor and effective stiffness components from a curated 0 degree dataset. The surrogate is incorporated into Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) calculations to enable rapid and accurate property prediction for arbitrary fiber orientations, significantly reducing computational cost compared to full FEA. In addition, the surrogate aids in simulation quality control by identifying anomalous cases, particularly in angled cases, where mesh distortion and boundary artifacts are common. This automated approach enables scalable, physics informed generation of validated property datasets, supporting efficient inverse design of aligned DFRCs.

2 BACKGROUND AND THEORY

Figure 1: (a) Basic RVE Model (b) RVE with fibers orientated at angle θ (c) Combined series calculation example for E_{22} and G_{12}

In the RVE workflow, two distinct but complementary micromechanical approaches are used to characterize, estimate, and predict composite stiffness under different loading directions: the Halpin–Tsai model for axial modulus E_{11} , and a simple series-rule model for transverse modulus E_{22} and in-plane shear G_{12} . These models are complimented by Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) via the ply-

stiffness matrix Q to rotate those base moduli to arbitrary fiber angles. Each approach is explained below in terms of its mathematical formulation, physical rationale as it relates to the RVE geometry as shown in Figure 1a and 1c, and specific examples of its application within this work.

2.1 Micromechanical Models

The stiffness of the DFRC RVE can be evaluated by analyzing the mechanics of the load transfer through its microstructural constituents. In the fiber axis direction, apart from the localized fiber to fiber gap region, where the fiber gap is small in absolute terms, most structural elements are aligned in parallel with high length to width aspect ratios. Under these conditions, the Halpin-Tsai formulation as shown in Equation 1, accurately captures the composite's longitudinal stiffness [10]. In this configuration, each RVE is defined by a global fiber volume fraction V_f , fiber modulus E_{f1} , and matrix modulus E_m , with the parameter η defined in Equation 2.

$$E_{11} = E_m \frac{1 + \xi\eta V_f}{1 - \eta V_f} \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = \frac{\frac{E_{f1}}{E_m} - 1}{\frac{E_{f1}}{E_m} + \xi} \quad (2)$$

Here, ξ is a dimensionless shape factor that encapsulates fiber aspect ratio, spacing, and interphase stiffness. As discussed previously, this factor is often determined experimentally based on fiber to fiber interactions [8,10]. As ξ approaches zero, the Halpin-Tsai equation predicts a lower bound consistent with the classical Reuss Model [11], while in the limit as ξ approaches infinity, the model converges to an upper bound akin to the Rule of Mixtures. For aligned discontinuous fiber based RVEs, ξ must account not only for the fiber aspect ratio but also for the efficiency of load transfer through the longitudinal matrix gaps between fibers.

In contrast, when the RVE is subjected to transverse loading or in-plane shear, the microscopic load path intersects matrix dominated regions before reaching the fiber reinforced domains. For example, the representative cross-sectional used to determine the transverse modulus E_{22} differs significantly from that used in the longitudinal case, both in geometry and in local stiffness distribution. As a result, applying the same Halpin-Tsai model to E_{22} and G_{12} yields inaccurate predictions, with the lower bound failing to capture the behavior observed in finite element simulations. To address this, a hybrid Reuss series model [7,12] is employed to estimate the transverse and shear moduli by decomposing the RVE into two distinct subregions; one consisting of a fiber and matrix region, and other composed solely of matrix filled fiber gap zones, as described in Equations 3 and 4. In this formulation, E_{f2} denotes the fiber transverse modulus, and the associated microstructural configuration is illustrated in Figure 1c).

$$E_{22} = \left(\frac{f_{stripe}}{E_{22stripe}} + \frac{1 - f_{stripe}}{E_m} \right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$E_{22stripe} = \left(\frac{f_{fiber}}{E_{f2}} + \frac{1 - f_{fiber}}{E_m} \right)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

A similar modeling approach is used to calculate the shear modulus. Since the matrix gaps function as the weakest link under loading, even a modest value of f_{gap} , defined as the length fraction

of transverse fiber gaps as shown in Figure 1a, can significantly reduce both E_{22} and G_{12} , driving them toward the matrix properties E_m or G_m . As a result, rather than using the Halpin–Tsai model, which assumes a uniformly mixed fiber and matrix medium, a simple series model more accurately captures the reduced transverse and shear stiffness observed in RVE data. This series model serves as a physically meaningful baseline estimate and does not require any fitted parameters such as ξ , thereby providing additional confidence in the quality of the initial training data. Nonetheless, machine learning models remain essential to account for the complex nonlinear interactions among geometric and material inputs that are not adequately captured by analytical formulations alone.

2.2 Stiffness Matrix

Once the base-case ply moduli have been determined and validated, they can be extended to RVEs with rotated fiber orientations (Figure 1b) to predict the composite’s overall behavior. Using Classical Laminate Theory, the validated values of E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} are implemented into the plane-stiffness matrix, Q , thereby transforming the 0 degree ply properties into the local coordinate system of an angled fiber system and allowing for the extraction of global moduli [13]. Equations 5-7 detail the basics of this transformation where values of Q_{xy} are functions of the global E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} for a 0 degree ply. The Q matrix is then rotated by transposition matrix $T(\theta)$ and inverted into a global compliance matrix S which holds the rotated values for E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} [11].

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{cases} Q_{11} = \frac{E_{11}}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \\ Q_{22} = \frac{E_{11}}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \\ Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{12}E_{22}}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \\ Q_{66} = G_{12} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$S = (T(\theta)QT(\theta)^{-T})^{-1} \quad (6)$$

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{12} & S_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{cases} E_{11}(\theta) = \frac{1}{S_{11}} \\ E_{22}(\theta) = \frac{1}{S_{22}} \\ G_{12}(\theta) = \frac{1}{S_{66}} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

These expressions describe how in-plane stiffness of a ply changes as its fibers rotate from 0 degrees to an arbitrary angle θ . In this study, once the stiffness values for plies with 0-degree fiber orientation are validated, they are incorporated into the transformed reduced stiffness matrix Q to estimate the mechanical properties of plies with rotated fibers. This approach enables the validation of more complex FEA geometries involving arbitrary fiber orientations.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Automated Representative Volume Element Generation

In this study, RVEs of aligned DFRCs were generated using a fully automated Python-driven workflow within the Abaqus environment. A Python driver script invokes Abaqus to generate 2D unit-cell models of aligned discontinuous fiber composites. Each cell contains a square polymer matrix of

size $L_x \times L_x$ and a prescribed number of straight fiber segments. Each RVE geometry was parameterized by four key microstructural variables: fiber length (L_f), fiber discontinuity gap (F_g), fiber width (F_w), fiber angle (θ) and fiber volume fraction (V_f).

In conventional composite RVE FEA, it is common practice to impose periodic boundary conditions (PBCs). These conditions enforce compatibility of displacement and traction across opposing faces, allowing the RVE to behave as part of an infinite periodic microstructure. This ensures accurate homogenization of effective mechanical properties [14,15]. However, in the present study, PBCs were not applied due to challenges introduced by angled fiber configurations. These configurations result in irregular meshing along the boundaries of RVE, making it impractical to maintain node to node correspondence across opposite faces, which is necessary for enforcing periodicity.

Instead, mechanical properties are extracted from global reaction forces generated by applied boundary conditions. In this approach, one edge of the RVE is fully constrained, while the opposite edge is subjected to a prescribed strain, ε . The resulting reaction forces on the boundaries are used to compute effective stiffness moduli, as shown in Equation 8. The quantity F_i represents the reaction force in either the longitudinal or transverse direction and is used to compute the corresponding modulus. The shear modulus is calculated using the built-in stress and strain volume averaging functionality within the FEA environment.

$$E_i = \frac{F_i * L_x}{\varepsilon} \quad (8)$$

To ensure that the RVE is statistically representative despite the absence of PBCs, a convergence study is conducted. The side length L_x of the RVE is systematically increased according to the relation:

$$L_x = N (F_l + F_g) + \delta, N = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (9)$$

where δ is a small buffer added to avoid edge truncation artifacts, and N is the number of repeated fiber and gap units included in the simulation domain. Simulations are conducted for each value of L_x at a fiber orientation angle of 0 degrees, and the corresponding moduli E_{11} and E_{22} are tracked. Once the moduli exhibit convergence with increasing L_x , the RVE is considered sufficiently large to capture microstructural variability and yield reliable estimates of bulk mechanical properties. To verify consistency across different configurations, additional simulations are performed using randomly generated angles θ , confirming convergence across all phases of interest.

3.2 Dataset Generation

The driver script functions as the primary tool for dataset generation. It automates the creation of a large set of RVE simulations, specifically targeting 0 degree fiber orientation cases. A master script controls this process by systematically modifying key geometric parameters, L_f , F_g , F_w , and V_f across a wide range of values as shown in Table 1. Sampling these parameter spaces enables the construction of a comprehensive dataset suitable for training predictive models. As discussed in Section 2, the 0 degree ply configuration serves as the baseline case for the modeling framework. These baseline simulations are validated through a combination of analytical predictions using the Halpin–Tsai model and the Reuss series formulations, as well as visual inspection of the simulated fiber and matrix microstructure. This validation process ensures that the generated data accurately captures the governing mechanics and provides a reliable foundation for model development.

In parallel, a second dataset was generated using the same automated workflow, varying the same geometric parameters as before, but with fiber angles assigned within $\theta \in [0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. This dataset captures a broader spectrum of microstructural variability and is intended for testing the generalization capability of the surrogate models. Unlike the baseline 0 degree cases, these angled configurations are

not used for training but rather serve as validation and application scenarios. Due to the computational expense associated with running full FEA for thousands of fiber angle combinations and manually validating results, this dataset highlights the necessity of the surrogate modeling approach. The combination of a targeted training dataset at 0 degrees and a broader set including randomized fiber orientations provides both accuracy in model calibration and coverage of geometrically diverse cases. This approach supports efficient property prediction across a wide range of composite configurations while reducing the computational cost associated with full finite element simulations.

Table 1: Key geometric parameters with respective ranges

Geometric Parameter	Variation Range
Fiber Length, (L_f)	5.0 – 40.0 mm
Fiber Discontinuity Gap (F_g)	0.1 – 4.0 mm
Fiber Width (F_w)	0.1 – 4.0 mm
Target Volume Fraction (V_f)	0.1 – 0.55

3.3 Surrogate Model Training and Application

To enable scalable and efficient prediction of effective mechanical properties across a wide range of fiber architectures, a surrogate modeling framework was developed. This framework is based on machine learning models trained exclusively on the high-fidelity simulation results from the 0 degree fiber orientation dataset. The surrogate combines direct regression models with a Classical Laminate Theory formulation to generalize predictions to arbitrary fiber angles, thereby significantly reducing the computational cost associated with full FEA runs. The surrogate model development begins with training three separate regression models to predict transverse modulus E_{22} , in-plane shear modulus G_{12} , and the Halpin–Tsai shape parameter ξ , which governs the longitudinal modulus E_{11} through a physics based equation. While E_{22} and G_{12} are directly predicted by regression models, the prediction of E_{11} requires an additional modeling step. This is due to complex load transfer mechanisms introduced by fiber discontinuities, which limit the ability of purely data driven models to directly capture the relationship between geometric parameters and the longitudinal modulus. Therefore, E_{11} is calculated using the Halpin-Tsai equation with the predicted value of ξ .

The input features for models include the fiber volume fraction, fiber gap length, fiber length, and fiber width. Random Forest Regression was selected due to its ability to capture nonlinear relationships, resistance to overfitting, and minimal hyperparameter sensitivity [16,17]. Each model was trained using standardized input features with an 80 to 20 training and testing split. Model performance was evaluated using the coefficient of determination R^2 and mean absolute error (MAE), with results showing high predictive accuracy and good agreement between model outputs and FEA data. Once trained, the regression models were coupled with Classical Laminate Theory to estimate global stiffness for fiber orientations beyond zero degrees. The predicted values of E_{11} , E_{22} , and G_{12} for the base 0 degree case were rotated using transformation matrices (Equations 5 through 7) to compute moduli for arbitrary fiber angles. This approach allows rapid estimation of in-plane moduli for any fiber angle without additional simulation, enabling efficient evaluation of a broad design space.

In addition to property prediction, the surrogate model is also used to detect erroneous data within the larger dataset of randomly oriented fiber configurations. When applied to this broader set, the surrogate helps identify cases that produce nonphysical results or exhibit large deviations from expected trends. These errors result from issues such as poor mesh quality, incorrect material assignment, or fiber placement failures, particularly in angled configurations where boundary conditions are more difficult to apply consistently. Anomalous cases are flagged and removed for further inspection, helping to ensure that only valid simulation results are used in future inverse design tasks. A representative instance of datapoint failure is visualized in Figure 2 showing improper assignment of fiber material to matrix regions, which would result in uncharacteristically high mechanical properties reported by FEA.

Through this entire process, the surrogate model not only accelerates property prediction but also ensures the reliability and physical consistency of the overall dataset.

Figure 2: Angled fiber geometry generated with erroneous material assignment

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As discussed in section 3.1, Figure 3 displays the results of the convergence study used to initially size RVEs for accurate statistical representation. For each N as shown in Equation 9, E_{11} , E_{22} , and G_{12} , were calculated for a variety of permutations of geometric variables. Three representative cases are shown in the figure. As N increased from 1 to 7, all three moduli changed by less than 2% variation beyond $N = 3$ in every trial. Based on this result, $N = 3$ was selected as the minimum RVE size that balances convergence of effective properties with computational efficiency. While the surrogate is trained on baseline FEA simulations and relies on their accuracy, it is also leveraged as a secondary validator when applied to large datasets with random fiber angles. In this role, the surrogate acts as a filter, flagging FEA cases that yield nonphysical or inconsistent results typically due to meshing, fiber placement, or boundary condition errors thereby enforcing dataset quality and reliability.

Figure 3: Moduli convergence with variation in number of simulated fiber and gap sections

Following the confirmation of RVE size, a dataset of 200 with 0 degree fiber orientations and varying geometric parameters was generated to train the Random Forest Regression model. Figure 4 presents parity plots illustrating the performance of each surrogate model. Figure 4c and 4d show predicted versus actual values for, E_{22} , and G_{12} , while Figures 4a and 4b display the predicted versus actual values for the Halpin-Tsai shape factor $\xi_{E_{11}}$, with Figure 4a showing the full range and Figure 4b focusing on a zoomed view to better illustrate accuracy in the relevant domain.

Figure 4: Random Forest parity plots for (a) $\xi_{E_{11}}$ (b) $\xi_{E_{11}}$ with range 0-50 (c) E_{22} and (d) G_{12}

While the full parity plot for $\xi_{E_{11}}$ in Figure 4a reveals a few outliers at higher values, their impact on the predicted E_{11} is minimal. Visual inspection of the corresponding data indicates that these outliers are associated with cases involving very high fiber lengths, where the resulting error in $\xi_{E_{11}}$ translates to deviation of less than 5% in the predicted modulus E_{11} . In the more relevant operational range shown in Figure 4b, the predicted and actual values of $\xi_{E_{11}}$ are nearly perfectly alignment, with overall $R^2 = 0.975$ and $MAE = 1.21$. The parity plots for E_{22} , and G_{12} also show tight clustering around the identity

line, demonstrating strong predictive accuracy. The computed performance metrics are $R^2 = 0.970$ and $MAE = 0.061$ GPa for E_{22} and $R^2 = 0.977$ with $MAE = 0.021$ GPa for G_{12} . Collectively, these results confirm that the Random Forest Regression models, when trained on data with $\theta = 0^\circ$ fiber orientations, are capable of accurately predicting transverse and shear stiffness and of reliably estimating the shape factor $\xi_{E_{11}}$. This estimated shape factor can then be used in the Halpin-Tsai equation to produce a representative value of E_{11} . The high level of agreement between predicted and actual values supports the use of these models in CLT-based validation for fiber angles beyond 0 degrees.

Applying the trained regressors to geometries with fiber orientations different from 0 degrees revealed important insights into the behavior of aligned discontinuous fiber composites under CLT. Initially, any trial in which either E_{11} or E_{22} deviated by more than 10% from the FEA result was discarded. However, this percentage-based criterion incorrectly flagged cases where one modulus was inherently much larger than the other. For example, when fibers are closely aligned with the loading direction, E_{11} may be significantly higher than E_{22} , or when a moderate angle is selected, both moduli may approach their minimum values. In such cases, even a small absolute discrepancy (e.g. 0.5 GPa) in modulus can correspond to a relative error exceeding 10 %. To address this issue, a dual thresholding method was implemented. A trial was retained if the absolute error in E_{11} or E_{22} was below 3 GPa and only excluded if both the percent error exceeded 10% and the absolute error was greater than 3 GPa. This approach ensures that low-modulus cases with small absolute deviations are preserved, while still eliminating predictions with both large relative and large absolute errors.

While this dual-threshold filtering improves the retention of valid data points, it also accepts lower accuracy in directions with inherently low stiffness. This compromise is reasonable for highly anisotropic plies, where structural performance is primarily governed by axial stiffness. It is also applicable to symmetric configurations that exhibits low values of both E_{11} and E_{22} , where accurate predictions across all directions remains essential to fully characterize composite behavior. Across the validation set, the mean absolute error was 0.98 GPa for E_{11} and 2.2 GPa for E_{22} , suggesting a bias introduced by training with 0 degree fiber orientation which favors accurate prediction of E_{11} . Figures 5a and 5b display retained data points for E_{11} and E_{22} , respectively. In conjunction with these plots, Figure 5d illustrates that many of the erroneously discarded points were in fact valid E_{11} or E_{22} dominated cases, or intermediate cases, in which 0.5 GPa error translated to a $> 10\%$ discrepancy.

In contrast, the surrogate model for shear modulus G_{12} performed poorly, with a mean absolute error of 1.35 GPa, even though typical G_{12} values remain below 4 GPa. As shown in Figure 5c, the model consistently overpredicts shear stiffness for aligned discontinuous fiber composites. Further analysis indicates that this discrepancy is not due to surrogate error but rather limitations in the underlying FEA data for rotated plies. Specifically, the simulated G_{12} values show minimal variation across fiber angles, clustering tightly around 1 GPa, despite expectations of greater anisotropy. This suggests that the global shear loading conditions in the current FEA configuration may not effectively engage the angle-dependent shear response of the fiber–matrix system. Importantly, this behavior highlights the surrogate model’s utility in identifying and flagging erroneous or unphysical FEA outputs. While G_{12} accuracy remains a limitation, it does not impact the validation of E_{11} and E_{22} , which are the primary moduli of interest in inverse design applications.

Although validation based CLT does not perfectly match FEA results, it provides a reasonable confidence range for E_{11} and E_{22} . In practice, CLT and other analytical methods are inherently approximate and cannot fully capture the complexity of microscale fiber interactions. Nonetheless, their ability to bound trends observed in simulation data lends credibility to the FEA results and justifies their use in inverse modeling where longitudinal and transverse stiffness are primary targets.

Looking ahead, future work must focus on improving both the FEA shear loading methodology and the surrogate model’s ability to predict lower stiffness values for E_{11} and E_{22} . This may include a wider range of off-axis fiber configurations and exploring hybrid modeling strategies that more

effectively integrate analytical theory, data-driven methods, and microscale physics.

Figure 5: Parity plot of Surrogate Application (a) E_{11} (b) E_{22} (c) G_{12} (d) Filtered Fea Data E_{11} vs E_{22}

6 CONCLUSIONS

An automated, surrogate-model-driven pipeline was demonstrated for generating and validating 2D RVEs of aligned discontinuous carbon fiber composites. Convergence studies confirmed that three repeated fiber gap units are sufficient to capture representative moduli without the use of periodic boundary conditions, offering a practical balance between accuracy with computational efficiency. A training dataset of 200 samples with 0-degree fiber orientation was used to train three Random Forest Regression models to predict transverse modulus E_{22} , shear modulus G_{12} , and the Halpin–Tsai shape factor $\xi_{E_{11}}$. The models achieved $R^2 > 0.97$ and $\text{MAE} < 0.07$ GPa on held out test data. The trained regression models were integrated into a Classical Laminate Theory based validation approach, enabling

rapid prediction of longitudinal and transverse moduli across arbitrary fiber orientations. Predictions for most configurations remained within 10% of corresponding FEA results. In addition to property prediction, the surrogate model was applied during post-processing to identify and flag anomalous FEA outputs from large datasets with random fiber orientations. This filtering step removed results that deviated from expected physical behavior, improving consistency and reliability of the dataset.

Together, this approach reduces computational expense by several orders of magnitude while generating a high-fidelity dataset appropriate for inverse design tasks. By combining physics-informed micromechanics with machine learning, it offers a scalable approach for tailoring composite microstructures to target properties. Future work must focus on improving both the FEA shear loading strategy to correctly analyze angle-sensitive G_{12} behavior, and the surrogate model's precision in predicting low moduli E_{11} and E_{22} cases more precisely.

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